

'Biginelli' Compounds as Potent Mimics of Dihydropyridines

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Recently much interest has been focussed on the chemistry of 2-oxo(or thioxo)tetrahydropyrimidine-5-carboxylic acids and their derivatives known as 'Biginelli' compounds. When properly substituted they can act as cardiovascular agents, which is not surprising since they can be regarded as aza-analogs of nifedipine related dihydropyridines¹. Suitably substituted 2-alkyl-1,4-dihydropyrimidines are reported to block calcium channels², while 2-heterosubstituted-1,4-dihydropyrimidines exhibit antihypertensive activity³. In the case of *N*-unsubstituted dihydropyrimidines, location of the double bonds is ambiguous due to their tautomerism⁴. However, the preferable tautomers depend on the kinds of substituents⁵.

6-Methyl-4-substituted-phenyl-2-oxo-1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyrimidine-5-carboxylic acid ethyl esters (**1a-h**) were synthesised by condensing substituted benzaldehydes with ethyl acetoacetate and urea in absolute ethanol as solvent⁶. The 2-thioxo derivatives (**2a-h**) were prepared in a similar way, using thiourea instead of urea⁷. Their pmr spectra showed a doublet at δ 5.52 due to 4-H which collapsed to a singlet on exchange with D₂O. A multiplet integrating for three protons appeared at δ 6.80–7.35, which was assigned to two aromatic protons at 2'- and 5'-positions and to the NH proton at position-1. The proton due to NH at position-3 was observed at δ 8.40–8.85 while a triplet due to 3H of the CH₃ of ethyl ester appeared at δ 1.16–1.23 and a quartet at δ 4.09 was assigned to the 2H of the OCH₂ of ethyl ester⁸.

The ir spectra exhibited bands for the secondary amino groups at 3 200–3 320 cm⁻¹, the ester carbonyl function at 1 700 cm⁻¹ and the ketone carbonyl group at 1 640 cm⁻¹. In addition, the aromatic and aliphatic C–H as well as C=C stretch were observed in the expected regions⁸ at 3 050, 2 900 and 1 550 cm⁻¹ respectively. Data of **1a-h** and **2a-h** are given in Table 1.

Effect on blood pressure and heart rate in nor-

motensive anaesthetised rats : Normotensive Charles Foster rats (350–460 g) were anaesthetised with sodium pentobarbitone (35 mg/kg i.p.). Blood pressure and heart rate were recorded on a 7D grass polygraph using Statham P 231D pressure Transducer and Grass 7P4G tacograph preamplifier respectively⁹. A polythene cannula was inserted in one of the jugular vein for drug administration. Test compounds were made as a fine homogenised suspension 1% (w/v) in 0.5% (w/v) gum acacia in normal saline and intravenous administration of the test compounds at dose range of 1–25 mg/kg body-weight displayed fall in blood pressure and heart rate for a short time and which recovered to predrug level. Compound **1a** at 25 mg/

a; R¹ = C₂H₅, R² = CH₃, R³ = CH₃

b; R² = C₂H₅, R³ = C₂H₅

c; R² = C₂H₅, R³ = CH₃

d; R² = CH₃, R³ = C₂H₅

e; R¹ = C₃H₇, R² = CH₃, R³ = CH₃

f; R² = C₂H₅, R³ = C₂H₅

g; R² = C₂H₅, R³ = CH₃

h; R² = CH₃, R³ = C-H

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF BIGINELLI COMPOUNDS (1, 2a-h)*

Compd. no.	M.p., °C/ (Yield %)	$\nu_{\max}$ (cm ⁻¹)	δ
1a	209 (49)	3 250, 3 075, 2 900, 1 705, 1 640, 1 615, 1 570, 1 495, 1 215, 1 050	1.20 (3H, t, ArCH ₂ CH ₃), 2.25 (2H, q, ArCH ₂ CH ₃), 2.56 (3H, s, 6-CH ₃), 3.83 (6H, s, 2 OCH ₃), 5.50 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 4.6 Hz, 4-H), 6.80–7.45 (3H, m, 3',6'-H and 1-NH), 8.40 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 4.6 Hz, 3-NH)
b	200 (44)	3 320, 3 055, 2 945, 1 700, 1 635, 1 615, 1 580, 1 515, 1 270, 1 055	1.16 (3H, t, ArCH ₂ CH ₃), 1.45 (6H, t, <i>J</i> 7.0 Hz, 2 OCH ₂ CH ₃), 2.30 (2H, q, ArCH ₂ CH ₃), 2.55 (3H, s, 6-CH ₃), 4.04 (4H, m, <i>J</i> 7.01 Hz, 2 OCH ₂ CH ₃), 5.52 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 4.6 Hz, 4-H), 6.75–7.50 (3H, m, 3'-H, 6'-H and 1-NH), 8.42 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 4.6 Hz, 3-NH)
c	155 (50)	3 300, 3 050, 2 915, 1 710, 1 640, 1 620, 1 550, 1 500, 1 250, 1 065	1.15 (3H, t, ArCH ₂ CH ₃), 1.45 (3H, t, <i>J</i> 6.9 Hz, OCH ₂ CH ₃), 2.37 (2H, q, ArCH ₂ CH ₃), 2.55 (3H, s, 6-CH ₃), 3.90 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 4.04 (2H, q, <i>J</i> 6.9 Hz, OCH ₂ CH ₃), 5.32 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 4.7 Hz, 4-H), 6.70–7.45 (3H, m, 3'-H, 6'-H and 1-NH), 8.43 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 4.7 Hz, 3-NH)
d	133 (44)	3 320, 3 010, 2 950, 1 700, 1 635, 1 615, 1 580, 1 500, 1 275, 1 030	1.16 (3H, t, ArCH ₂ CH ₃), 1.40 (3H, t, <i>J</i> 7.0 Hz, OCH ₂ CH ₃), 2.25 (2H, q, ArCH ₂ CH ₃), 2.56 (3H, s, 6-CH ₃), 3.86 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 4.04 (2H, q, <i>J</i> 7.0 Hz, OCH ₂ CH ₃), 5.50 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 4.7 Hz, 4-H), 6.80–7.45 (3H, m, 3'-H, 6'-H and 1-NH), 8.45 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 4.7 Hz, 3-NH)
e	190 (53)	3 300, 3 050, 2 925, 1 710, 1 635, 1 620, 1 575, 1 500, 1 270, 1 065	0.96 (3H, t, ArCH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃), 1.50 (2H, m, ArCH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃), 2.56 (5H, m, ArCH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃ and 6-CH ₃), 3.97 (6H, s, 2 OCH ₃), 5.30 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 4.5 Hz, 4-H), 6.75–7.50 (3H, m, 3'-H, 6'-H and 1-NH), 8.42 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 4.5 Hz, 3-NH)
f	187 (54)	3 250, 3 070, 2 920, 1 710, 1 640, 1 615, 1 565, 1 505, 1 275, 1 055	0.96 (3H, t, ArCH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃), 1.50 (6H, t, 2 OCH ₂ CH ₃ and 2H, m buried, ArCH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃), 2.55 (5H, m, ArCH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃ and 6-CH ₃), 4.05 (4H, m, 2 OCH ₂ CH ₃), 5.35 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 4.7 Hz, 4-H), 6.80–7.50 (3H, m, 3'-H, 6'-H and 1-NH), 8.40 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 4.7 Hz, 3-NH)
g	126 (40)	3 320, 3 050, 2 925, 1 700, 1 635, 1 615, 1 575, 1 500, 1 280, 1 035	1.0 (3H, t, ArCH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃), 1.46 (3H, t, OCH ₂ CH ₃ and 2H, m buried, ArCH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃), 2.56 (5H, m, ArCH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃ and 6-CH ₃), 3.85 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 4.04 (2H, q, OCH ₂ CH ₃), 5.40 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 4.7 Hz, 4-H), 6.75–7.50 (3H, m, 3'-H, 6'-H and 1-NH), 8.42 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 4.7 Hz, 3-NH)
h	172 (48)	3 200, 3 010, 2 940, 1 705, 1 625, 1 550, 1 495, 1 210, 1 080, 1 035	1.0 (3H, t, ArCH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃), 1.50 (3H, t, OCH ₂ CH ₃ and 2H, m buried, ArCH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃), 2.55 (5H, m, ArCH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃ and 6-CH ₃), 3.83 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 4.04 (2H, q, OCH ₂ CH ₃), 5.32 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 4.7 Hz, 4-H), 6.70–7.45 (3H, m, 3'-H, 6'-H and 1-NH), 8.42 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 4.7 Hz, 3-NH)
2a	149 (48)	3 200, 3 010, 2 950, 1 705, 1 625, 1 550, 1 495, 1 210, 1 080, 1 035	1.19 (3H, t, ArCH ₂ CH ₃), 2.40 (2H, q, ArCH ₂ CH ₃), 2.56 (3H, s, 6-CH ₃), 3.95 (6H, s, 2 OCH ₃), 5.30 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 4.5 Hz, 4-H), 6.85–7.60 (3H, m, 3'-H, 6'-H and 1-NH), 8.43 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 4.5 Hz, 3-NH)

NOTE

Table-1 (Contd.)

b	188 (44)	3 320, 3 050, 2 900, 1 710, 1 630, 1 580, 1 515, 1 275, 1 200, 1 055	1.15 (3H, t, ArCH ₂ CH ₃), 1.46 (6H, t, 17.0 Hz, 2 -OCH ₂ -CH ₃), 2.35 (2H, q, ArCH ₂ CH ₃), 2.55 (3H, s, 6-CH ₃), 4.05 (4H, m, 17.0 Hz, 2 -OCH ₂ CH ₃), 5.32 (1H, d, 4.7 Hz, 4-H), 6.75-7.60 (3H, m, 3'-H and 1-NH), 8.40 (1H, d, 4.6 Hz, 3-NH)
c	134 (52)	3 300, 3 010, 2 900, 1 700, 1 620, 1 575, 1 520, 1 250, 1 095, 1 050	1.19 (3H, t, ArCH ₂ CH ₃), 1.45 (3H, t, 17.01 Hz, OCH ₂ -CH ₃), 2.42 (2H, q, ArCH ₂ CH ₃), 2.56 (3H, s, 6-CH ₃), 3.87 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 4.05 (2H, q, 17.01 Hz, OCH ₂ CH ₃), 5.35 (1H, d, 4.6 Hz, 4-H), 6.70-7.55 (3H, m, 3'-H, 6'-H and 1-NH), 8.45 (1H, d, 4.6 Hz, 3-NH)
d	158 (54)	3 310, 3 050, 2 920, 1 700, 1 625, 1 555, 1 500, 1 250, 1 200, 1 065	1.20 (3H, t, ArCH ₂ CH ₃), 1.46 (3H, t, 17.01 Hz, OCH ₂ -CH ₃), 2.30 (2H, q, ArCH ₂ CH ₃), 2.56 (3H, s, 6-CH ₃), 3.83 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 4.05 (2H, q, 17.01 Hz, OCH ₂ CH ₃), 5.40 (1H, d, 4.5 Hz, 4-H), 6.80-7.60 (3H, m, 3'-H, 6'-H and 1-NH), 8.41 (1H, d, 4.5 Hz, 3-NH)
e	187 (47)	3 200, 3 070, 2 900, 1 710, 1 630, 1 500, 1 495, 1 210, 1 100, 1 030	0.99 (3H, t, ArCH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃), 1.45 (2H, m, ArCH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃), 2.58 (5H, m, ArCH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃ and 6-CH ₃), 3.96 (6H, s, 2 -OCH ₃), 5.35 (1H, d, 4.6 Hz, 4-H), 6.80-7.65 (3H, m, 3'-H, 6'-H and 1-NH), 8.45 (1H, d, 4.6 Hz, 3-NH)
f	200 (50)	3 250, 3 080, 2 950, 1 700, 1 625, 1 550, 1 515, 1 270, 1 200, 1 055	1.0 (3H, t, ArCH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃), 1.50 (6H, t, 2 -OCH ₂ CH ₃ and 2H, m buried, ArCH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃), 2.56 (5H, m, ArCH ₂ -CH ₃ and 6-CH ₃), 4.04 (4H, m, 2 -OCH ₂ CH ₃), 5.32 (1H, d, 4.5 Hz, 4-H), 6.75-7.70 (3H, m, 3'-H, 6'-H and 1-NH), 8.45 (1H, d, 4.5 Hz, 3-NH)
g	128 (44)	3 320, 3 050, 2 925, 1 700, 1 630, 1 550, 1 510, 1 275, 1 175, 1 030	0.97 (3H, t, ArCH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃), 1.48 (3H, t, OCH ₂ CH ₃ and 2H, m buried, ArCH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃), 2.55 (5H, m, ArCH ₂ -CH ₂ CH ₃ and 6-CH ₃), 3.80 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 4.06 (2H, q, OCH ₂ CH ₃), 5.35 (1H, d, 4.7 Hz, 4-H), 6.70-7.65 (3H, m, 3'-H, 6'-H and 1-NH), 8.40 (1H, d, 4.7 Hz, 3-NH)
h	170 (48)	3 250, 3 010, 2 915, 1 710, 1 630, 1 575, 1 510, 1 250, 1 200, 1 065	0.96 (3H, t, ArCH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃), 1.49 (3H, t, OCH ₂ CH ₃ and 2H, m buried, ArCH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃), 2.56 (5H, m, ArCH ₂ CH ₂ -CH ₃ and 6-CH ₃), 3.82 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 4.05 (2H, q, OCH ₂ CH ₃), 5.32 (1H, d, 4.5 Hz, 4-H), 6.70-7.75 (3H, m, 3'-H, 6'-H and 1-NH), 8.43 (1H, d, 4.5 Hz, 3-NH)

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

kg body-weight i.v. produced 22 mm/Hg fall in blood pressure for 30 min and **1g** elicited 12-52 mm/Hg decrease for 6-35 mins, while other compounds produced transitory action (Table 2).

Experimental

M.ps. were determined on a Buchi melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. Pmr spectra were recorded on Varian T-60A (60 MHz) and Jeol Fx90Q

(90 MHz) spectrometers using TMS as internal standard and ir spectra on a Shimadzu IR-435 spectrophotometer.

6-Methyl-4-substituted-phenyl-2-oxo(or thioxo)-1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyrimidine-5-carboxylic acid ethyl esters (1a-h, 2a-h): A mixture of urea (or thiourea) (0.10 mol), 2,4-dialkoxy-5-alkylbenzaldehyde (0.10 mol), ethyl acetoacetate (0.15 mol) and ethanol (50 ml) containing concentrated HCl (10 drops) was refluxed for

13–15 h and the solvent was then removed under reduced pressure. The gummy mass was then column chromatographed using petroleum ether-ethyl acetate (90 : 10) as eluant.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF TEST COMPOUNDS ON BLOOD PRESSURE AND HEART RATE IN ANAESTHETISED RATS*

Compd. no.	Dose mg/kg (i.v.)	Fall in B.P. mm/kg	Duration min
1a	1–10	–	–
	1–25	22 ^a	30
b	1–10	15	Tr
	1–25	15 ^a	8
c	1–25	3–45	Tr
g	1–25	12–52 ^a	6–35
2a	1–25	10–25 ^a	Tr
	1–25	40–50	Tr
c	1–25	–	–
e	1–10	–	–
	1–25	50 ^a	6
g	1–25	40–60	5

*Each value is the mean of three experiments; (–) = nil activity, Tr = transitory activity (1–3 min).

^aTransitory decrease in heart rate by 5–10 beats/min.

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